

Improved Artificial Neural Network Algorithm for Offline Signature Verification

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Abstract

Identity theft is an invasive crime globally because most people have their information available online. Research has shown that an effective signature verification system can be used to mitigate the impact of identity theft on society. In this paper, we design an efficient similarity index to resolve the shortcomings of the existing measures in giving high confidence in signature verification. The experiment shows the efficacy of the proposed method in verifying offline signatures using an artificial neural network approach.

Keywords: Offline Signature, Artificial Neural Network, Signature Verification.

1 Introduction

In view of the current issues of identity theft, security in financial institutions, legal institutions, educational institutions, etc., has been heightened and is becoming an important and exacting task. Signature verification is used to mitigate the impact of identity theft on society. There is an urgent need to find an accurate and reliable automated system that is able to classify signatures as either genuine or forgery in order to identify impostors.

Signature verification has therefore become the focus of current research and has received significant attention from academics; many techniques and methods for verifying signatures have been proposed and applied. However, until now, there has been no method that offers the required accuracy in verifying offline signatures using neural networks. This challenge is mainly due to the features extracted from the signature for verification [1, 4].

Figure 1: Artificial Neural Network Architecture [14]

Generally, there are two classes of signature extraction methods: function and parameter approaches. The function approach is used in dynamic systems where the signature is characterized in terms of a time function, such as position, velocity, pressure, etc. The parameter approach is used when the signature is represented as a vector of elements, where each element represents a specific feature [5]. The two subcategories of parameter approaches are global and local features. In the global approach, features are extracted from the overall signature image [6, 7]. Conversely, in the local approach, features are extracted from specific parts of the signature image [5]. The choice of features selected in a signature verification system is essential, and it must be made in such a way that it is suitable for the application [8].

In most signature verification systems, the similarity between a trained database image and a reference image is computed. A matching algorithm is designed and used to predict the similarity between the two images [7, 8]. Hidden Markov Model, Neural Networks Approach, Template Matching Approach, Statistical Approach, and Support Vector Machine are some of the techniques used to verify signatures.

The development of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is motivated by a biological neural network. Its ease of use has made it a widely used technique in pattern recognition. The network is divided into three layers: Input, hidden and output [9]. The image of the signature is introduced at the input layer, the hidden layer takes care of computation, and the output layer collects and transmits results for given inputs. ANN must be trained before it can discriminate between genuine signatures and forgeries.

Signature verification systems can be categorized into offline and online techniques [1, 8, 9]. Offline signatures, which are also known as static signatures, are hard to verify because they have fewer distinctive features and are more widely used for personal verification and identification than online signatures, which are also known as dynamic signatures [6].

In an offline or static signature verification technique,

images of the signature to be verified are obtained from a piece of paper using a camera or a scanner [6, 10]. The scanned signature images are preprocessed and subjected to feature extraction before being verified. This technique relies on the static characteristics of the signature, which are invariant [10]. An offline signature verification technique does not require any special acquisition hardware, making it relatively less invasive and user-friendly [6].

The aim of a signature verification system is to classify signatures as genuine or forgery. These classifications are as a result of intrapersonal and interpersonal variations. Intrapersonal variation is the variation of signatures of same person, while interpersonal variation is the variation between genuine and forgeries [6]. Forgery in biometrics (signature) is an attempt by an impostor to hoodwink people into believing that someone else's signature belongs to him. Signature forgery is classified into random forgery, simple forgery, and skilled forgery [9]. In this paper, we proposed an improved artificial neural network algorithm for offline signature verification by extracting the following features (Aspect Ratio, Occupancy Ratio, Centroid, Slope of the Centre of Gravities, Horizontal Projection Positions, and Corner Points) from the signature datasets used in this study. In order to verify the findings of [1, 4] that there is a significant correlation between improved feature extraction techniques and the accuracy of an offline signature verification system, we set up two experimental methods (proposed method and control method).

We used the purposive sampling technique to select eight members of the population involved in the study that wrote thirty genuine signatures, imitated fifteen skilled forged signatures, and fifteen simple forgeries each.

2 Literature Review

Signature verification is a biometric technique that uses the characteristics of a person's signature to validate the identity of the individual. It is the most popular form of biometric identification, but it is less accurate than some other biometrics, such as; fingerprints, iris recognition, facial recognition, etc. [1, 6]. It is a technique used by intelligence agencies, banks, and high-profile institutions to authenticate the identity of an individual.

Signature verification is not only applicable as a research area in image processing and pattern recognition but is also widely used for human identification in access control, finance, security, and contractual matters [8]. The proliferation of potent forgery technologies has engendered the interest of concerned persons and institutions to develop an effective verification system that will detect and counter forgeries.

Signature verification systems are used to classify signatures into genuine or forgery. Signature forgery is a technique used by impostors to imitate a genuine signa-

ture with the aim of finagling someone else's resources. It is classified into random, simple, and skilled forgeries [9].

The authors in [1] proposed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based signature verification system to prevent fraud by malicious people. Their method consisted of separately trained CNN architects for Writer Dependent (WD) and Writer Independent (WI) signatures. They used GPDS synthetic signature dataset, which consists of 4000 different persons' signatures. Every person has 24 genuine signatures and 30 forged signatures. In the first model, CNN was trained via Writer Dependent (WD) signatures. Thirty signatures (15 genuine and 15 forgeries) of an individual were selected at random to train the network. Other 24 signatures were used to test the trained network. Convolutional Neural Network was via Writer Independent (WI) signatures in the second model. A total of 540 signatures which consisted of 240 genuine and 300 forgeries from ten persons, were used. Three hundred signatures (150 genuine and 150 forgeries) were selected at random and used to train the network. Other 240 signatures were used to test the trained network. Their results showed that Writer Independent (WI) has an accuracy of 62.5%, and Writer Dependent (WD) has an accuracy of 75%. They concluded that the obtained results would increase if the Convolutional Neural Network method is supported by additional feature extraction methods.

Rampur proposed a system that had local texture features and feed forward back propagation in an artificial neural network classifier to authenticate and classify the signatures of individuals [2]. Rampur, S.M. posits that the feature extraction phase is the most significant phase in any recognition system because the accuracy of the system depends on the extracted features from the signatures. Local features like entropy, energy, correlation, homogeneity, and contrast were extracted from the signatures. A different set of signatures were fed into the network for recognition. When 20 persons' signatures were fed into the network for training and recognition, 99% accuracy was achieved. Accuracies of 98.3%, 97%, 96%, and 95% were achieved when 40, 60, 80, and 95 persons' signatures were introduced into the network, respectively. The author concluded that the performance of the system could be increased by using additional features in the dataset. The system proposed gave 90-99% accuracy based on the number of input signatures.

The authors in [3] proposed an offline signature verification system using a neural network. The small parts of the signature image were split according to the centre of gravity, and three features (pixel density, cell angle, and pixel angle) were extracted from each part of the signature image. A total of 100 signatures each from ten persons were used to train and test the network. Mean features of the trained signature images were used as input to the network. The hidden layer of the neural network

contained 50 neurons, and the output layer contained one neuron. An accuracy of 90% was achieved.

Shukla et al. in [4] developed a system for the verification of signatures based on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to prevent human error during the signature process and lower chances of fraud in the process of authentication. They extracted the wavelets, shadow, texture of the signature and graphometric and geometric of the signature, and designed a Convolutional Neural Network with seven network layers, eight neurons in a layer, learning rate of 0.25, and initial weight of 1. The authors got and showed results for the area of the image, centroid, eccentricity, skewness, and kurtosis. The database of 400 signatures was tested. They achieved test accuracy of 89% and validation accuracy of 93%. The authors concluded that the accuracy of 89% could be increased to 95% with minimization of errors and increased CNN layers.

Kumar, M. presented an improved offline signature verification system using global and texture features of signatures [11]. Artificial Neural Network (ANN) was used to train and verify the signature datasets and the proposed system discriminated between genuine and forged signatures (random, simple, and skilled). Kumar, M. posits that feature extraction is the key to identifying and differentiating a user's signature from another which makes it an important step in developing any signature verification system. Global features like signature height-to-width ratio, signature area, maximum horizontal and maximum vertical histogram, horizontal and vertical centre of the signature, and edge point number of the signature were extracted from the signatures. Texture features like homogeneity, contrast, entropy, and correlation were extracted from the signatures. A total of 310 signatures from 40 persons were used for training and testing of the signature recognition and verification system. The input layer of the Artificial Neural Network contained nine neurons, the hidden layer comprised ten neurons, and the designed network consisted of 200 epochs. A False Acceptance Rate (FAR) of 6.67% and a False Rejection Rate (FRR) of 13.33% were achieved for 60 tested signatures. The author concluded that the system could be improved by changing the features that were extracted from the signature.

Zulkarnain et al. in [12] posit that too many features may decrease the False Rejection Rate (FRR) but also increase the False Acceptance Rate (FAR). They stated that a low value of FAR and FRR is required to obtain an accurate verification result. The authors proposed a combination of current global features such as horizontal distance, vertical distance, hypotenuse distance, and angle. The difference between the mean of the standard deviation ratio of each feature was used to achieve better accuracy. They used the GPDS-960 database, which consists of 23049 genuine and 28800 forgeries obtained from 960 individuals. For their work, they used 200

datasets, which comprised 100 genuine and 100 forged signatures, and presented four new features (horizontal distance, vertical distance, hipotenuse distance, and angle). The authors used the equation proposed by [13] to select the six best features out of the 13 proposed features by them. The six best features (aspect ratio, pure height, maximum horizontal histogram, horizontal distance, vertical distance, and hipotenuse distance) were selected because they had the largest value of mean/standard deviation difference. Three (horizontal distance, vertical distance, and hipotenuse distance) out of four of the presented new features were included as best features. The authors compared the proposed method with seven previous studies that did not apply the best features selection method. The proposed method had an accuracy of 87.5% which is higher than the compared non-feature selection method. The authors concluded that selecting the best features among huge features will help improve the performance of a signature verification system.

3 Signature Verification concept

The verification of offline signature involves the following steps:

1. Data Acquisition: In offline signature verification, we can acquire data by collecting signatures from a signature database or scanning a signature image and converting it to a digital image [8].
2. Image preprocessing: Image preprocessing involves the enhancement of input images [6]. This technique is used to improve the features of raw images by removing distortions [2]. The preprocessing steps are not limited to Binarization, Thresholding, Noise Reduction, Width Normalization, Thinning, and Bounding.
3. Feature Extraction: After image preprocessing, feature extraction is the next stage in the verification process. Functions and parameters are the two types of features that can be used. In dynamic systems, function features are used because the signature is characterised in terms of a time function, such as position, velocity, pressure, etc. Parameter features are used when the signature is represented as a vector of elements, where each element represents a specific feature [5]. Generally, feature extraction of function features has shown better performance than parameters, but the matching process requires time-consuming procedures.

Parameters are classified into two subcategories: Global and local. Global features are extracted from the overall signature image, and provide information about the entire structure of the signature [6], [7]. Global features include Signature area, Signature width to height ratio (Aspect ratio), Pure

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Offline Signature Verification System

width, Pure height, Image area, Maximum horizontal histogram, Maximum vertical histogram, and Orientation.

Local features are extracted from specific parts of the signature image. Local parameters can be divided into two subcategories: Component-oriented parameters and pixel-oriented parameters. Parameters are component-oriented when the feature extraction is at the level of each component (e.g., stroke orientation, height to width ratio of the stroke, etc.). The parameters are pixel-oriented when feature extraction is at the pixel level (e.g., pixel density, texture, grid-based information, gray-level intensity, etc.) [5].

The choice of features selected in a signature verification system is very important. The selection must be made in such a way that it is suitable for the application [6, 8].

4. Classification Classification is carried out on the basis of features extracted from signature. It uses decision rules to divide feature into different classes. Artificial Neural Network is used as a classifier in a signature verification system. In classification, test images are compared with trained data images to classify test images.

Figure 3: Comparing the different types of signatures.

3.1 Types of forgeries and Performance Evaluation

Signature forgery is classified into random forgery (Figure 3), simple forgery, and skilled forgery [9]. These are explained below:

1. Random forgery: This is very easy to detect as compared to other forgeries because the impostor creates a signature in his own style without having information such as the signature shape and structure of the person whose signature is to be forged.
2. Simple forgery: The impostor has the legitimate writer's name and signature style and creates a signature with the same shape or the genuine writer's name.
3. Skilled forgery: The legitimate signature is made by an impostor after several practices. The forged signature is quite challenging to detect.
4. Signature samples: (a) Genuine Signature (b) Random Forgery (c) Simple Forgery (d) Skilled Forgery.

3.2 Performance evaluation

The performance of a signature verification system is appraised according to the error representation of the system. The two quantities used to characterize the performance of the signature verification algorithm are False Rejection Rate (FRR) and False Acceptance Rate (FAR).

False Rejection Rate (FRR): This is also known as Type-I error. It is the proportion of times a biometric system fails to allow an authorized person to access it. Mathematically, the False Rejection Rate (FRR) is the ratio of the total number of genuine signatures rejected to the

total number of genuine signatures tested by the system represented as a percentage.

False Acceptance Rate (FAR): This is also known as Type-II error. It is the proportion of times a biometric system allows an unauthorized person to access it. Mathematically, False Acceptance Rate (FAR) is the ratio of the total number of forged signatures accepted to the total number of forged signatures tested by the system represented as a percentage.

Average Error Rate (AER): This is computed by taking the average of Type-I and Type-II errors.

Equal Error Rate (EER): This is also known as Crossover Error Rate (CER). It is the crossing point in the graph plotted as False Acceptance Rate (FAR) vs. False Rejection Rate (FRR).

4 Method

For the purpose of this research, an experimental method was used as a research tool because the effects of independent variables on dependent variables were measured. This method, also known as empirical research or cause and effect method is data-based research, with conclusions capable of being verified with observation or experiment [15].

The success of collecting data depends on the method applied. In carrying out any successful research, there are various methods of collecting data; however, the method to be used is dependent on the nature of the data needed [16]. Therefore, it is essential to use the correct methods and obtain data from the most appropriate sources to obtain accurate data.

The authors in [17] underscored two main sources of data for general research purposes, primary and secondary sources. The data used for this study was collected from the primary source. The data was collected from eight persons using a purposive sampling technique.

MATLAB R2019b Neural Network Toolbox which contains the MATLAB tools for designing, implementing, visualizing, and simulating neural networks, was used for the purpose of this study. The Graphical User Interface (GUI) used in this study was created with MATLAB GUIDE.

5 Experimental Result

In this study, a Back Propagation Neural Network is proposed to prevent signature fraud by impostors. The proposed system includes two major stages: training and testing. An algorithm is designed to verify whether the input signature image corresponds to the signature image in the trained database.

The training stage consists of four significant steps: Retrieval of a signature image from a database; Preprocessing of a signature; Extracting features of the signature by

Figure 4: Scaling of signature image

feature extraction techniques; Training neural network via back propagation.

The testing stage consists of five significant steps: Retrieval of a signature to be tested from a database; Pre-processing of a signature; Extracting features of the signature by feature extraction techniques; Applying extracted features to a trained neural network; Examining output generated from a neural network, and declaring a signature as genuine or forgery.

Data acquisition: Signature samples are collected on white A4 paper using different pens at different timing under different emotions such as stress and joy levels. The signature image is scanned by a scanner at a resolution of 600 dpi and saved with .jpg file format. For training and testing of the signature verification system, 480 signatures are used. The signatures were collected from 8 persons. Eight persons wrote thirty genuine signatures and imitated each other's signatures. Each of the eight persons wrote 15 skilled and 15 simple forgeries. In the training set, the total number of signatures is 320 (160 genuine signatures, 80 skilled forgeries, and 80 simple forgeries). For testing, 160 signatures (80 genuine signatures, 40 skilled forgeries, and 40 simple forgeries) are used.

Image pre-processing: In this study, the techniques used for image pre-processing are: Image scaling, RGB to Gray Scale Conversion, Binarization, and Thinning.

Image scaling: The features extracted from a signature will change if the size of the signature of the same person changes. Hence the accuracy of the verification system reduces. The signature has to be scaled to a specific size before feature extraction to avoid a reduction in the accuracy of the verification system (Figure 4, 5).

RGB to Gray Scale conversion: The scaled signature image, which is in the form of red, green, and blue, is converted to grayscale with the following formula : $GrayScale = (0.299 * R) + (0.5876 * G) + (0.114 * B)$. RGB to Gray Scale conversion is done before extracting features from signature because processing a colored image is slower than a grayscale image. The hue and saturation information of the colored image is eliminated, while the luminance is retained.

Binarization: Grayscale image is converted to a binary image (black and white image) using Otsu's method. The signature is represented in black pixels, and other areas

Figure 5: Scaling of signature image

Figure 6: Binarization of image

are in white pixels.

Thinning: This is used to eliminate thickness differences in signature (Figure 6) by making the image one pixel thick. Thinning is done because there is a possibility that the signature is written with different pens, and thickness thus varies from one pen to another. Few foreground pixels are eliminated, while signature strokes are represented with minimum cross-sectional width.

5.1 Proposed method

Feature extraction: The following features (Aspect Ratio (F1), Occupancy Ratio (F2), Centroid (F3), Slope of the Centre of Gravities (F4), Horizontal Projection Positions (F5), and Corner Points (F6)) are extracted from preprocessed signature image, and proposed to improve the accuracy of the offline signature verification system.

5.2 Control method

The following features (Area, Centroid, Entropy and Mean) are extracted from the preprocessed signature image and used as a control to compare the accuracy derived from

Figure 7: Thinning of image

the proposed method.

5.3 Signature verification

The features F1 to F6 are extracted from signature images of different persons. The features extracted from each person's signature samples are used to derive mean signature features for each person. Then all the features of a query signature are extracted to calculate the Euclidian distance with respect to the mean signature features of the original (training) signature images (Figure 7 and 8). The values of the minimum and maximum Euclidian distance of training signature images are used to set the acceptance range of the system. The tested signature is declared genuine if the Euclidean distance of its image with respect to the mean signature is within the acceptance range; otherwise, it is declared a forgery. Three different percentages have been used to measure the performance of the system. These are False Rejection Rate (FRR), False Acceptance Rate (FAR), and Accuracy. For the purpose of this work, 90% is chosen as a threshold (Table 1 and 2, Figure 8).

5.4 Algorithm for Signature Verification using Euclidian Distance

- STEP 1: Read a set of signatures belonging to a person into the work space.
- STEP 2: Scale each signature to a specific size.
- STEP 3: Convert each colored signature image into gray image and binary image.
- STEP 4: Perform Thinning on the converted image.
- STEP 5: Rotate the binary images so that all signatures can have equal inclination based on the baseline slant.
- STEP 6: Extract the features F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, and F6 from each signature and store them in a feature matrix.
- STEP 7: Dataset is created by computing the mean signature feature values.
- STEP 8: Calculate the Euclidian distance of query signature features from the mean signature features of the dataset.
- STEP 9: The query signature is verified as genuine if the distance is below a threshold of 90%; otherwise, it is detected as a forgery.

Figure 8: Input Image: This is the signature to be verified by the neural network.

5.5 Graphical User Interface

The Graphical User Interface (GUI) used for this study is developed using MATLAB R2019b GUIDE. Through the GUI, the user can select the signature database of interest, train the network with the content of this database, and verify the signature.

Reference Image: This is the signature that has been trained by the neural network which is to be compared to the input image.

Gray Conversion: This is the preprocessing technique that is used to convert the input image to grayscale.

Filtered Image: This is an enhanced input image that has been preprocessed.

ROI of Input Image: A region of interest (ROI) of an input image is the portion of the input image that is to be filtered or a portion that you want to perform some other operations on. An ROI is defined by creating a binary mask, which is a binary image with pixels that define the ROI set to 1 and other pixels set to 0.

ROI of Reference Image: A region of interest (ROI) of a Reference Image is the portion of the reference image that is to be filtered or a portion that you want to perform some other operations on. An ROI is defined by creating a binary mask, which is a binary image with pixels that define the ROI set to 1 and other pixels set to 0.

Proposed Experiment:

$$FRR = (0/80)100 = 0\%; FAR = (0/80)100 = 0\%$$

Control Experiment:

$$FRR = (5/80)100 = 6.25\%; FAR = (2/80)100 = 2.5\%$$

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed two experimental methods to check the effect of features extracted from a signature on the accuracy of an offline signature verification system.

Table 1: Results for Proposed Experiment.

		Tested	Rejected	Tested	Accepted	Tested	Accepted
1	Jemilatu	10	0	5	0	5	0
2	Adedoyin	10	0	5	0	5	0
3	Omolola	10	0	5	0	5	0
4	Merit	10	0	5	0	5	0
5	Tochi	10	0	5	0	5	0
6	Blessing	10	0	5	0	5	0
7	John	10	0	5	0	5	0
8	Adewumi	10	0	5	0	5	0
	Total	80	0	40	0	40	0

Table 2: Table showing Performance Evaluation

Experiment	FRR (%)	FAR (%)	Accuracy (%)
Proposed	0	0	100
Control	6.25	2.5	95.63

Figure 9: Chart showing the accuracy of the system in percentage (%)

Our proposed algorithm yielded an outstanding result. This type of verification analysis, if applied effectively by researchers and pertinent industries, can help develop a state-of-the-art system that would curb identity theft. In our study, the proposed experiment resulted in higher accuracy than the control experiment. Furthermore, the artificial neural network is an effective method in offline signature verification, and the features extracted from the signature dataset affect the accuracy of the system.

Conflicts of Interest

There is no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

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